

THE sKAR-CUNG INSCRIPTION

By H. E. RICHARDSON

COPIES OF EARLY INSCRIPTIONS from the collection of the Lama Rig-'dzin Tshe-dbang Nor-bu (RT) have been the basis of articles in *JRAS*, 1969 and 1972. Another of his texts, described as "from the *rdo-rings* at sKar-cung rgyal-sde itself", is the inscription on a stone pillar at Ra-ma-sgang near Lhasa which I edited with some remarks on its site and history in *JRASB*, 1949. It was included also by Professor G. Tucci in *Tombs of the Tibetan kings*, Rome, 1950 (*TTK*), where it was brought more fully into relation with a connected edict (*bka'-tshigs*) of Khri lDe-srong-brtsan recorded in vol. *ja* of the *Chos-'byung* of dPa'-bo gTsug-lag Phreng-ba (PT).

The pillar is in good condition. Competent Tibetans made a copy of the inscription for me. I also photographed it in detail and checked the results on several occasions. Professor Tucci, to whom I gave a copy of the text, later visited the site and examined the pillar.

Comparison with the editions of Professor Tucci and myself shows that RT's copy is much inferior. By itself it hardly warrants a new edition; but a few errors found their way into the published texts and the punctuation of the original has not been quite accurately reproduced. Moreover, Professor Tucci published a translation of the connected edict only and not of the inscription itself; and there is room for improvement in my version made in 1949. It is desirable, also, to consider further, according to Professor Tucci's own suggestion, a tentative hypothesis advanced by him in *TTK* questioning the authenticity of the inscription. The text is, therefore, edited once again, with a revised translation, notes, and commentary.

The transcription published below owes very little to RT, whose version can be seen from my photographs to contain a large number of mistakes. Many are relatively unimportant discrepancies, common to other RT MSS, due to modernization of the orthography: all the reversed *ki-gu*, *da-drag* and archaic *ya-btags* are omitted; *btsan* is substituted for *brtsan*, *la-sogs-pa* for *las-stsogs-pa* and so on. But there are also mistakes of substance which do not occur in RT's other texts. Whole passages have been omitted owing to the copyist's eye jumping ahead; and words and phrases have been completely misread. There are some 30 such instances in addition to the numerous orthographic differences but there seems no point in giving a list of variants that are demonstrably due to careless copying; and only in a few passages where the original is damaged or where the photographs are not clear will RT's readings be mentioned.

The reason for the poor standard of his text may be that it was impossible for RT to examine the pillar. His copies, it seems, were made some time before they came into his possession, that of the Lhasa Treaty Inscription as long as 250 years before. In three of them there are notes and corrections which show that they were compared with the original and there is evidence in the case of the Lhasa Treaty Inscription that this was done by RT himself in 1744 ("A Tibetan antiquarian of the 18th century", *Bulletin of Tibetology*, Gangtok, IV, 3, 1967). But by 1920 the pillar had been buried in an accumulation of sand from which it was excavated by the 'Brug-pa Lama bDe-chen Chos-'khor Rin-po-che, who rediscovered its existence. Perhaps at the time of RT's visit to Lhasa it was already concealed from view.

The text in Tibetan can be seen at pp. 104–108 of *TTK*. Points where the transcription that follows differs from it are summarized at the end of the notes below.

THE sKAR-CUNG INSCRIPTION

1. 'phrul gyi lha btsan po khri lde srong brtsan gyi ring
2. la || dam pa'i chos yun tu brtan bar¹ gtsigs
3. brnan pa² ||
4. 'phrul gyi lha btsan po | myes | khri srong brtsan gyi
5. ring la || sangs rgyas kyī chos mdzad de || ra sa'i gtsug
6. lag khang las stsogs pa brtsigs shing³ || dkon mchog
7. gsum gyi rten btsugs pa dang || myes | khri 'dus srong gi
8. ring la || gling khri rtse las stsogs par | gtsug lag
9. khang brtsigs ste || dkon mchog gsum gyi rten btsugs
10. pa dang || myes | khri lde gtsug brtsan gyi ring la || brag mar gyi
11. kva cu⁴ dang | mching phur gtsug lag khang brtsigs ste || dkon
12. mchog gsum gyi rten btsugs pa dang || yab | khri srong lde
13. brtsan gyi ring la || brag mar gyi bsam yas las stsogs
14. pa || dbung⁵ mthar gtsug lag khang brtsigs ste || dkon
15. mchog gsum gyi rten btsugs pa dang || lha btsan po | khri |
16. lde srong brtsan gyi ring la yang | skar cung gtsug lag khang
17. las stsogs pa brtsigs ste || dkon mchog gsum gyi rten
18. btsugs pa las stsogs pa || gdung rabs rgyud kyis |
19. 'di ltar sangs rgyas kyī chos mdzad pa 'di || nam du yang ma
20. zhig | ma btang na || legs pa dpag du myed par 'gyur ||
21. btang ste | zhig gam | myed par gyur na || sdig pa grangs myed
22. par 'ong bas || da phyin chad nam nam zha zhar || 'phrul gyi lha
23. btsan po | yab | khri srong lde brtsan gyi ring la || dkon mchog
24. gsum gyi rten btsugs pa dang || sangs rgyas kyī chos mdzad pa
25. myi gtang ma zhig par || gdung rabs rgyud kyis yi dam bca'o
26. zhes 'byung ba las stsogs pa || btsan po yab sras || rje
27. blon | kun kyis dbu snyung dang bro bor te || gtsigs kyī yi ge dang |
28. rdo rings la bris pa bzhin du yang mdzad do || 'di ltar || yab
29. myes | gdung rabs rgyud kyis || dkon mchog gsum gyi rten
30. btsugs shing || sangs rgyas kyī chos mdzad pa 'di || gces spras ci
31. la yang || sdig go zhe'am | ma legs so zhes | mo dang rmyi ltas las
32. stsogs ste | ci'i phyir yang rung ste | myi gzhig go | myi spang ngo || de skad

¹ RT reads *brtan pa'i*. Tucci and I agree on *brtan bar*; cf. F. W. Thomas, *Tibetan literary texts and documents (TLTD)*, II, pp. 94 (A2), 95 (A1), 98.

² RT reads *bsnan pa*. My photograph is not clear but in l. 55, where RT again reads *bsnan*, the word is unmistakably *brnand*.

³ RT reads *brtsigs ste* which appears also in ll. 9, 11, 14, and 17. The pillar is slightly damaged but Tucci and I both read *brtsigs shing*, which I have retained. The meaning is not affected.

⁴ The reading *tsu* in my edition and Tucci's may be due to an accidental mark on the stone; and I accept RT's *kva-cu*, which is also found in the edicts of Khri Srong-lde-brtsan and Khri lDe-srong-brtsan (*TTK*, pp. 98; 101).

⁵ RT correctly reads *dbung*. In my text and Tucci's *dbud* is in error.

33. ces | che chung sus gsold kyis kyang | de ltar myi mdzad do || btsan
 34. po dbon sras || sku chu ngur bzhugs pa yan cad || chab srid kyi
 35. mnga' bdag mdzad pa man cad kyang || dge slong las | dge ba'i
 36. bshes nyen bskos ste | chos thugs suci chud chud du bslab cing || bod
 37. yongs kyis kyang chos slob cing spyad pa'i sgo myi gcad | nam du yang bod ya
 38. rabs man cad | bod 'bangs las thar par gzud pa'i sgo myi bgag
 39. par | dad pa'i rnam las thar par btsud de || de'i nang nas
 40. nus pa las || bcom ldan 'das kyi ring lugs rtag du bsko
 41. zhing || bcom ldan 'das kyi ring lugs byed pa'i rnam chos 'khor
 42. nas bya'o cog gi bka' la yang btags ste || chos 'khor gyi las dang
 43. dbang byed cing | dge ba'i bshes nyen byed par bsko'o || rab du byung ba'i
 44. rnam || nged yab sras kyis | mchod gnas su gnang ba bzhin du byas
 45. ste || btsan po'i | pho brang na dkon mchog gsum gyi rten btsugs shing|
 46. mchod pa yang || gu du myi spang myi bskar zhing | mchod gnas su bgyi'o ||
 47. mdor na || btsan po'i | pho brang dang | bod khams na | dkon mchog gsum myed
 48. pa dang | spang ba'i thabs ci yang myi mdzad do || yab myes dbon sras
 49. gang gi ring la yang rung ste | dkon mchog gsum gyi rkyen bcad pa'i rnam
 50. kyang ma dma's ma zhig pa'i chos su || lha ris kyi khyim yig gi mgo nan las
 51. 'byung ba bzhin du chis mdzad do⁶ || da phyin chad gdung rabs re re zhing yang |
 52. btsan po yab sras kyis | 'di bzhin du yi dam bca'o || de las mna' kha
 53. dbud pa dag myi bgyi myi bsgyur bar || 'jig rten las 'das pa dang | 'jig
 54. rten gyi lha dang myi ma yin pa thams cad kyang | dpang du gsol te || btsan po|
 55. rje blon kun kyis kyang | dbu snyung dang | bro bor ro || gtsigs brnand pa'i
 56. yi ge zhib mo ni || yab kyi ring la gtsigs kyi yi ge bris pa'i zla la|
 57. bzhag go ||

The lines have been numbered for ease of reference. The reversed *ki-gu* is shown in italic.

The only significant differences in the above transcription from the text in Tibetan script at *TTK*, pp. 104–108 are as follows: l. 11 *cu* for *tsu*; l. 14 *dbung* for *dbud*; l. 25 *kyis* for *kyi*. Two further errors in my Tibetan text in *JRASB*, 1949, have been corrected, viz. l. 30 *btsugs* for *bcugs* and l. 44 *mchod* for *mchos*. Minor discrepancies in orthography and punctuation are as follows: l. 18 *kyis* for *gyis*; ll. 39, 40, 43 *de* for *te*; and l. 55 *pa'i* for *ba'i*. Differences in the form of the *ki-gu* are in ll. 4, 10, 32, 44, 45, and the punctuation has been corrected in ll. 7, 11, 12, 14, 15, 16, 20, 23, 27, 28, 32, 36, 38, 43, 44, 46, 48, 50, 51, 53, 55.

In translating the inscription I have had valuable help from Mr. Samten Karmay, a Tibetan scholar with a good knowledge of English; but the language of the early 9th century is often obscure and the precise meaning of some passages remains in doubt. It is difficult also at times, even when the meaning is clear, to follow the Tibetan construction very closely. For example the passage from l. 4 to l. 28 is a continuous sequence of dependent clauses. I have divided it into three sentences; and readers of Tibetan will readily identify other such adjustments.

⁶ RT reads *mi mdzad do*, which is clearly mistaken. I have discussed the word *chis* in *Asia Major*, XIV, 2, pp. 254–256.

For ease of comparison with Professor Tucci's translation of the connected edict in *TTK*, pp. 51–54, I have adopted his rendering of the recurring words and phrases *rten*, *gtsug lag khang*, and *dkon mchog gsum* as “receptacles”, “temple”, and “the three jewels”.

TRANSLATION

“In the time of the divine manifestation, the king, Khri lDe-srong-brtsan: an edict made to confirm that the holy religion shall be maintained for ever.

In the time of the divine manifestation, the ancestor, Khri Srong-brtsan, in practising the religion of the Buddha, receptacles of the three jewels were established by building the temple of Ra-sa and so on;⁷ and in the time of the ancestor, Khri 'Dus-srong, receptacles of the three jewels were established by building the temple of Khri-rtse in gLing and so on;⁸ and in the time of the ancestor, Khri lDe-gtsug-brtsan, receptacles of the three jewels were established by building the temples at Kva-cu and mChing-phu in Brag-mar and so on;⁹ and in the time of the father, Khri Srong-lde brtsan, receptacles of the three jewels were established by building temples at the centre and on the borders,¹⁰ bSam-yas in Brag-mar and so on; and in the time of the divine king, Khri lDe-srong-brtsan also, receptacles of the three jewels were established by such acts as building the temple at sKar-cung and so on. As for the practice of the religion of the Buddha in this way by successive generations, if it is never destroyed or abandoned, good beyond measure results; but if it is abandoned or destroyed, there come sins without number. Therefore, from now onwards, for ever and ever, following the pronouncement in the time of the divine manifestation, the king the father Khri Srong-lde-brtsan, that each generation should take a vow not to abandon and not to destroy the receptacles of the three jewels and the practice of the religion of the Buddha, the king the father and sons, ruler and ministers, all together, shall swear an oath and shall act in accordance with the words of the edict and the inscription on the pillar. If someone should say: “This practice of the religion of the Buddha by establishing in this way receptacles of the three jewels by the father and ancestors in successive generations, to hold it in esteem, for whatever purpose, is a sin” or “it is not good”,¹¹ whether that be said because of divination or omens in dreams or for any reason whatsoever, it shall not be destroyed; it shall not be abandoned. And whoever utters such words, be he great or small, let nothing of that sort be

⁷ This and the parallel passage in the edict (*TTK*, pp. 51, 52) are the earliest evidence, little more than 150 years after Srong-brtsan sGam-po's death, that he was regarded as the founder of Buddhism in Tibet.

⁸ 'Dus-srong was at Khri-rtse in 701 and 702 and at gLing in 703, in which year he was also campaigning in 'Jang—the Nanchao kingdom (J. Bacot, F. W. Thomas, and C. Toussaint, *Documents de Touen-houang relatifs à l'histoire du Tibet*, Paris, 1940 = *THD*, pp. 39, 40). Although the identification of early place names with those of the present day is not always reliable, those activities on the border make it probable that the gLing of the inscription is the region in eastern Tibet north of sDe-dge.

⁹ The temple of Kva-cu in Brag-mar survived as the small chapel of Ka-chu in the neighbourhood of bSam-yas. Its name perhaps commemorated the destruction by the Tibetans in 727, during the reign of Khri lDe-gtsug-brtsan, of the fortress of Kua-chou on the far north-western frontier of China, not far from Tun-huang. From about 776 the city, which appears in Tibetan records as Kva-cu, was regularly occupied by them.

¹⁰ *dbung-mtha'*, “centre and periphery”, might be an epithet describing the great temple of bSam-yas, which stands at the centre of a circular walled precinct with subsidiary temples at cardinal points all round it in representation of the Buddhist concept of the universe. But a wider reference is suggested by *THD*, p. 114, where Khri Srong-lde-brtsan is said to have founded temples “everywhere, in the centre and on the borders”—*dbus mtha' kun tu gtsug lag khang brtsigs te | chos btsugs*.

¹¹ I do not think that either Professor Tucci or I got this passage right. *gces spras ci la yang* appears to be part of what the unbelievers may say.

done. But from the time when the king, his sons, and grandsons are young until the time when they become rulers of the kingdom and thereafter, too, teachers of virtue from among the monks shall be appointed and by teaching religion, as much as can be absorbed into the mind,¹² the gate of deliverance for all Tibet through the learning and practice of religion shall not be closed. And when for all Tibetan subjects, from the nobles downwards, the gate for entering deliverance is never obstructed and when the believers have entered upon deliverance, from those among them who are able there shall always be appointed followers of the tradition of the Buddha.¹³ And those who carry on the tradition of the Buddha shall be appointed to act as teachers of virtue, adhering to all such conduct as is commanded in the Wheel of the Law and exercising the duties and authority of the Wheel of the Law.¹⁴ As for those who enter the priesthood we, father and sons, shall appoint them as chaplains and shall cause them to act as chaplains, establishing receptacles of the three jewels in the king's palace and not neglecting or restricting the offerings of worship.¹⁵

In short, in the palace of the king and in the land of Tibet, by no means soever shall anything be done to destroy or abandon the three jewels. And in the time of the father, grandfather, grandsons, and sons, whoever it may be, because of the religious obligation that property assigned to the support of the three jewels should never be reduced or destroyed, due attention shall be given¹⁶ to the effect of the strict provisions in the register of households of the monastic estates. And from now onwards also, in each generation the kings, father and son, shall take an oath accordingly. And so that there may be no detraction from that sworn pledge and no change in it, the king, the ruler with his ministers, all together, calling as witnesses the saints, the gods that have left the world, the gods who are of the world, and all spirits, have sworn a solemn oath;¹⁷ and as for the detailed text of the

¹² The construction of the greater part of the text is impersonal, with rare indications of the agent. There is only one personal pronoun—*nged* . . . *kyis* in l. 44. Here we might understand either that the teachers taught the kings, or the kings learned, as much religion as possible.

¹³ *ring lugs*, which is quite common in MSS from Tun Huang of this period, seems to have a wide range of meaning. In *TLTD*, II, pp. 59, 162, and 406 Thomas translates it as "old usage", but that is dubious, for in a large number of other instances it implies an official function connected with the attesting of documents: e.g. Lalou, *Inventaire des manuscrits... de Touen-houang... (LINV)*, no. 1078, *ring lugs gyi sug rgya*; no. 1081, *ring lugs gyis zhus pa*; no. 1084, *ring lugs gyis bris ste*; or with the communication of orders, e.g. *THD*, p. 23, *zlags gyi ring lugs bkye*; p. 27, *gcod pa'i ring lugs* . . . *bkye*; or with records, e.g. *TLTD*, II, p. 139, *zhing 'god kyi ring lugs*. In such cases Thomas suggests the meaning "courier" or "commissioner" (*TLTD*, II, 16); the former is too restricted and, in view of the mention of a *ring lugs blon* (*LINV*, 2204), too lowly. "Commissioner" is better; but the apparent connexion with custom and precedent suggests something like "registrar". The term is found less often in MSS in a religious context: e.g. *ring lugs bande* (*LINV*, 1002), but is quite specific in the inscriptions at lCang-bu and Zhwa'i Lha-khang (*TTK*, p. 89; *JRAS*, Oct. 1952, p. 154). The former mentions the *bcom ldan 'das ring lugs kyi 'dun sa*—"the assembly of the Buddha *ring-lugs*"; the latter (ll. 59–62) directs that a repository be secured, in the presence of more than three reliable *ring-lugs*, with the seal of the *ring-lugs*. In current Tibetan the word refers to tradition or doctrine, e.g. *Grub-mtha' shel gyi me-long*, *kha f.44 a*, *rje bla ma'i ring lugs*. A senior teacher or abbot who transmits a doctrine or carries on a religious tradition may be described as *ring-lugs-'dzin*; and it is to that sort of duty that the passage in ll. 40–43 of our inscription relates.

¹⁴ "The Wheel of the Law": the preaching of the Buddha.

¹⁵ *bskar-ba* is not clear to Tibetans I have consulted. A connexion with *dgar-ba* (Jäschke, p. 20) suggests the meaning "set apart, restrict".

¹⁶ *mgo-nan*. Das, p. 285, translates "first, foremost" but gives no examples. As *nan* connotes pressure or urgency perhaps the sense is, rather, "to give priority". I have taken it here to refer to important rules for safeguarding monastic endowments.

¹⁷ ll. 51–55 repeat almost exactly the last lines of the bSam-yas pillar, which is probably the *rdo-rings* referred to in l. 28.

confirmatory edict, it has been deposited alongside¹⁸ the text of the edict written in the time of the father."

Before discussing the authenticity of the inscription something may be said about the identification of the site. Later historians variously record that Khri lDe-srong-brtsan built a temple at sKar-chung or dKar-chung in dBu-ru kLungs-shod (*rGyal-po bka'-thang*), rGya-sde (*sBa-bshed* and Bu-ston), rGyal-sde (*Hu-lan deb-ther*), and sKyi-shod (dPa'-bo gTsug-lag). The *guide to the holy places of central Tibet* by mKkyen-brtse Rin-po-che mentions a dKar-chung *mchod-rten* in 'On; but it is not suggested as the site of Khri lDe-srong-brtsan's foundation; and on a visit to 'On I found no trace of any inscribed pillar there or any early chapel except for Ke-ru lha-khang which is attributed to Khri Srong-lde-brtsan.

RT clearly identifies sKar-cung with the chapel at Ra-ma-sgang, and that was also the view of sDe-chen Chos-'khor Rin-po-che; but it was questioned by monks of 'Bri-khung, who claimed that rTsa Pho-brang in kLung-shod was the true site. As mentioned in *JRASB*, 1949, p. 46, I visited that place to look for evidence but found none.

Later records generally indicate a site near Lhasa. In the *Chos-'byung* of Bu-ston it is said that at the restoration of Buddhism in Central Tibet, 'Bring Ye-shes Yon-tan built a chapel at Ngan-lam spyi-mo between sNye-thang and sKar-chung, which latter chapel, also, he maintained. He then built 'Dan Ra-mo-che. 'Bring, by some accounts was one of the Ten Men of dBu who brought back the faith from Khams in 978. He is recorded as having lived until about 1020 (George N. Roerich (Jr.), *The Blue Annals*, Calcutta, 1949-53, p. 324). Ngan-lam spyi-mo is unidentified but sNye-thang and 'Dan (or Bran) Ra-mo-che are respectively 20 and 8 miles down river from Lhasa. The *Blue Annals* further attribute the building of a chapel at sKar-chung to the disciples of 'Bring.

A discrepant note is introduced by the *Chos-'byung* of Taranatha with the statement that certain Indian kings are named on the pillar at sKar-chung. There is nothing of the sort in our inscription or in the connected edict and, although it is possible that a second pillar lies buried at Ra-ma-sgang, Taranatha may have confused the sKar-cung inscription with that at the tomb of Khri lDe-srong-brtsan in 'Phyong-rgyas, where Indian kings do appear to have been named (*JRAS*, 1969, p. 33).

On the whole, the fact that a pillar mentioning sKar-cung stands at Ra-ma-sgang and was known, at least in the 18th century, as the sKar-cung inscription supports the identification. Further, and impressive, evidence is provided by the site itself. Although only a very small chapel survived in recent times, the former importance of the place is proclaimed by the extensive area marked out by four great *mchod-rten* with one more at the centre. Remains of similar size and arrangement survive also at 'U-zhang, a few miles down river from Ra-ma-sgang, which is claimed as the site of a great religious foundation by Khri lDe-srong-brtsan's son Khri gTsug-lde-brtsan (Ral-pa-can). Although at neither place is there any sign of a circular enclosure wall or of subsidiary chapels, the pattern clearly recalls that of bSam-yas, built as a model of the Buddhist concept of the universe. No other sites comparable with these three appear to have been recorded; and, perhaps, the design was peculiar to the first flowering of Buddhism between c. 760 and 830. At all events, it may be asked,

¹⁸ *zla-la*, literally, "as a pair to".

since the only famous religious foundation specifically attributed to Khri lDe-srong-brtsan was sKar-cung, where else can it be sought except where the impressive remains and the inscribed pillar are to be seen, at Ra-ma-sgang?

Professor Tucci's question about the authenticity of the inscription is not due to any doubt about the site, which he accepts as sKar-cung. Comparison of the text with the *bka'-tshigs*—the edict recorded by dPa'-bo gTsong-lag—gave him the impression that the inscription had been modernized. He does not imply an intention to deceive; but suggests that, perhaps, "at the time of the *phyi dar* in order to establish the antiquity of the place . . . the ancient document preserved in the archives was actually engraved on the stone in modernized form" (TTK, p. 69).

The first sign he notices is that the inscription does not contain the use of *re* with a negative sense which appears in the *bka'-tshigs*: e.g., where the latter has *gzhig re spang re* the inscription has *myi gzhig go | myi spang ngo*. The *re* form is found elsewhere in early MSS in the wording of oaths (THD, pp. 105, 110) but it is not used on inscribed pillars of the same period where the context is similar, e.g. at Zhwa'i Lha-khang; and it is particularly noteworthy that the inscription on the pillar at bSam-yas, which is earlier than that at sKar-cung and whose authenticity has not been questioned, contains similar provisions to those in the sKar-cung inscription and in the same form—without *re*. The construction with *re*—a sort of rhetorical question: "how should one do such a thing?"—may have been a literary usage while a direct prohibition may have been deemed more suitable for public inscriptions. But, as the two modes of expression were contemporary, it cannot be claimed that one is more modern than the other.

Professor Tucci's second point in doubt is "the aberrant reading mC'ings p'u for mC'ims p'u", which latter form, it is implied, appears in MSS from Tun-huang both as the name of a clan and as a place name (TTK, pp. 69; 83–84, n. 124). There is some confusion here. First, the name in the inscription is not *mChings* but *mChing*. Secondly, although the clan name *mChims* and the place name *mChims-yul* occur often in Tun-huang documents, *mChims-phu* is not found. On the other hand, *mching*, also, appears in early documents (F. W. Thomas, *Ancient folk literature from N. E. Tibet*, p. 124, LINV 1039 and 1285), perhaps as an epithet rather than as a place name but, nevertheless, a valid word of that period. Certainly, in later histories the name of the cave temple near bSam-yas generally appears as *mChims-phu*, but one MS of the *rGyal-rabs gsal-ba'i me-long* has 'Ching-phu; and it is noticeable that RT's copy, which tends to "correct" old reading into the form with which the copyist was familiar, has 'Ching; not *mChims*. There is nothing to show that Brag-mar, where the chapel is specifically stated to have been built, was ever part of *mChims-yul* and it is possible that the form *mChims-phu* was popularized by historians after the *phyi-dar* because the name of the *mChims* clan was well known to them from sources such as the *bKa'-thang sde-nga* as a link with the period of the kings. So far from being an "aberrant", *mChing-phu* here may well be good evidence of antiquity; and, even if it were an aberrant form, that would be slender evidence for the modernization of a text in which such uses as the reversed *ki-gu*, the *da-drag*, *las-stsogs-pa*, etc., have been retained.

Another point raised by Professor Tucci is that the historian dPa'-bo gTsong-lag, whose accuracy is shown by his, almost exact, transcription of the text on the pillar at bSam-yas, does not mention the sKar-cung pillar although he reproduces the edict in full. That need

cause no surprise. It was at bSam-yas that he wrote his history. The edicts which he reproduces are expressly stated to have been deposited in the archives there; and every time he entered the temple he would see the inscription on the pillar near the main door. Even so, a few small discrepancies are found. But when he refers to the Lhasa Treaty Inscription of 822 (vol. *ja*, f. 132a) he is so sketchy and inaccurate as to make it unlikely that he had ever seen the original. Between 1545 and 1566, when dPa'-bo gTsug-lag was writing, feelings often ran high at Lhasa between the bKa'-rgyud-pa sect, to which he belonged, and the dGe-lugs-pa, which was steadily growing in strength. The atmosphere would not have been attractive to a scholar; and there is no evidence that he ever went there or to the nearby Ra-ma-sgang.

Comparison of the two documents shows that ll. 30–51 of the inscription have an almost exact counterpart in the *bka'-tshigs*. Only the form with *re* has been changed and a few sentences of the *bka'-tshigs* have been omitted from the passage between ll. 43 and 44 of the inscription. But in the remaining 36 lines—i.e. the greater part of the inscription—there is no such close correspondence. The preamble about the establishment of temples is much longer and contains details not found in the edict. As already mentioned, mChing-phu is not named in the edict; nor is 'Dus-srong's temple of Khri-rtse, a foundation of which there appears to be no other record than that found in this inscription. The title '*phrul-gli lha-btsan-po*, seen here and in several other inscriptions of the early 9th century, is not found in Khri lDe-srong-brtsan's edict, or in those of Khri Srong-lde-brtsan, or on the pillar at bSam-yas; nor, although in later histories 'Dus-srong is called '*phrul-gyi rgyal-po*, does knowledge of '*Phrul-gyi lha-btsan-po* as a general title of the early kings appear to have survived. The invocation of various deities to witness the oath does not appear in the edict but is identical with a passage in the bSam-yas inscription. These differences and especially the addition of details unknown in the edict go strongly against the view that the inscription is a later redaction "in such a way as to be more easily understood by the common people" rather than a complementary and contemporary document.

In addition to the internal evidence there are many considerations of a practical and historical nature which make it improbable that the pillar was inscribed at the time of the *phyi-dar*—the second diffusion of the faith beginning at the end of the 10th century.

After the publication of my article in *JRASB*, 1949, I revisited Ra-ma-sgang with bDe-chen Chos-'khor Rin-po-che, who arranged to have the base of the pillar, which I had not seen before, cleared of sand. It is a massive block of stone, carved with a stylized Chinese design of mountains, supporting the monolith some 14½ feet tall by 3½ feet broad on top of which is a fluted stone canopy in the Chinese manner, surmounted by a finely carved stone ornament, apparently of Indian inspiration. The expense, labour, and craftsmanship involved in quarrying, transporting, and engraving this great monument—impressive even for the age of the kings—would have been beyond the resources of any group of monks at the *phyi-dar*. Central Tibet was then recovering from the social and economic fragmentation that followed the break-up of the kingdom about 150 years before; and the *Blue Annals* (pp. 61–62) show that the early monastic communities had to struggle to survive. Few of their foundations attained prosperity; and at Ra-ma-sgang the superb pillar and the large area with its great *stupas*, dating from an earlier age, were a striking contrast with the poor and tiny chapel of more recent times.

There is, it is true, one inscribed pillar which probably dates from the *phyi-dar*—that

at rGyal Lha-khang (*JRAS*, April 1957). Although rGyal was famous as the richest foundation of its day (A.D. 1012), the pillar is much smaller and simpler than that at sKar-cung. It is not a single stone but is made up of two separate blocks; and there is no hint of Chinese motifs. It is, indeed, questionable whether the mountain design, which appears at sKar-cung, would have been used at the *phyi-dar* when intimate contact with Chinese culture had been interrupted since the end of the T'ang dynasty, and was not renewed until the Yüan dynasty after which Chinese motifs became quite common in Tibetan art.

It may be noticed, incidentally, that in the 16 surviving lines of the rGyal inscription there is no example of the reversed *ki-gu* or the *da-drag* which are found in the sKar-cung text; and the only archaism is the *ya-btags* in the word *myi*.

It seems unnecessary to produce further arguments to dispel any reasonable doubt that the sKar-cung inscription is a shortened, contemporary statement of an important pronouncement the detailed text of which, too long to be inscribed on a stone pillar, was deposited, as the inscription itself states, together with that of the edict made in the time of the king's father. The latter must be the first *bka'-tshigs* of Khri Srong-lde-brtsan which was written in gold on blue paper, placed in a golden box, and deposited in the treasury at bSam-yas (*TTK*, p. 44); and it is to that document that the bSam-yas inscription (*TTK*, p. 94) refers when recording that "a detailed text of the edict exists separately", *gtsigs gyi yi ge zhib mo ni gud na mchis so*. The preamble in the *Chos-'byung* of dPa'-bo gTsug-lag to the edict of Khri lDe-srong-brtsan (*TTK*, p. 51) shows that the son followed a similar procedure, the only difference being that the box in which the text of his edict was deposited in the treasury at bSam-yas alongside that of his father was made of *phra-men* instead of gold.

The opportunity may be taken of mentioning that on the pillar at bSam-yas the words *Om A : Hum* : appear above the first line of the inscription, lightly engraved in *lan-tsha* characters. This invocation, which has so far escaped notice, is in a different style from the rest of the inscription; it is not accurately aligned with it, and is probably a later addition.